

Supplementary Figure 1. Body weight changes in the experimental period. G1, non-irradiated control group administered saline; G2, UVB-irradiated control group administered saline; G3 and G4, UVB-irradiated test agent groups administered OBS-E at doses of 50 and 200 mg/kg BW/day, respectively